

TEACHERS' ROLES IN ENHANCING PROFESSIONALISM IN THE EDUCATION INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Professionalism is a set of standards that an individual is expected to adhere to in a workplace usually in order to appear serious, uniform or respectful. The focus of every teacher who is ready to contribute values to education sector and programmes should be to attain professionalism. Despite the significant roles professionalism plays, there is lack of universally accepted definition of professionalism in teacher education programs. This study investigates teachers' roles in enhancing professionalism in the education industry which brings about diversity in learning activities through commitment. The findings show the need to display exemplary behavior-attitude, strength, teaching skill, knowledge and beliefs through diversify learning activities in effective professional ways. Teacher professionalism needs support on policy, moral, infrastructure, and financial that can lead them to excellent achievement. The study looked into the key principles of teacher education which is to attract competent people into the teaching profession as well as producing capable teachers that will build a virile nation. Finally, this work looked into the importance of professional development to teacher. This is the belief that education is a moving element and never-ending process and that learning does not stop after earning a degree and starting a career. It goes through continuing education where career-minded individuals can constantly improve their skills and become more relevant and proficient at their jobs.

Keywords: Professionalism, Teacher, Development, Students, Programmes, Standards, Education

Introduction

Professionalism is an individual adherence to a set of standards, code of conducts or collection of qualities that characterized accepted practices within an area of activity. Professionalism is also defined as the conduct, aims, or qualities that characterized or mark a profession with a number of different attributes. This involves consistency achieving high standards, both visibly and behind the scene. This can be further described as person's abilities, competence, and behavior in a particular profession. It aims at higher standards, more remarkable performance, and better connections with clients and co-workers. Evidence shows that there is an increase in education orientation, which has positively affected human and economic growth as well as other related institutions, Education is a basic need for human development and a key driver for sustainable society (Cheng, 2017). In order to deliver quality education, it is imperative for higher institutions especially universities which is considered as service centers with the capacity to target markets based on the standards of quality delivery. Education is the foundation for the renewal and transformation of our societies. It mobilizes knowledge to help us navigate a transforming and uncertain world. The power of education lies in its capacities to connect people with the rest of the world in order to move beyond spaces already occupies, and to expose human to new possibilities, helps to unite and provides the science knowledge and innovation that is needed to address common challenges in our societies. Education nurtures the understanding and builds capabilities that can help to ensure that the futures are more socially inclusive, economically just, and environmentally sustained. The roles of teacher in supporting modernization and sustainable development in Nigeria cannot be overemphasized. It is clear evident that no profession can adequately train man like in the education sector and be successful without competent teachers to drive the process. Quality teacher education is a sine qua non for the development of a developing country like Nigeria. A carefully planned and executed teacher education programme will result into greater gaps of teaching techniques, self-assurance and improved quality of education programmes. This will impact on the structuring of teacher education policy and the continuity of teacher learning. Again, teacher education provides a solid base of knowledge, skills and responsibilities that teachers need to perform their tasks and which continuous professional training allows for updates and adaptation to change. Continuous professional development is an integral element of teachers' responsibilities which needs to be anticipated with initial teacher education. Education programmes will be effective when they are based on teachers' needs and also allow for interaction among teachers (Victoria, 2015). Enhancement of teachers' professional competence is achieved when there is close contact and diverse interaction with the environment as well as being able to anticipate and influence factors which will bear upon teaching in the future. A good understanding of concepts and instructional strategies is necessary in presenting different aspects of the instructional process.

Most African countries have made drastic efforts towards repositioning teacher education programmes. For instance, Nigeria and Zambia shared common principles of training their teachers towards attainment of attitudes, skills and knowledge considered desirable towards making them efficient and effective in their work in accordance with the needs of the society. In specific terms, in Zambia, provision of quality pre-service and in-service teacher training programme has been the main focus of their Ministry of Education (Fredrick 2012) and in Nigeria, Kabiru (2012) stated that Nigeria has formulated a National Policy on Education. Teacher professionalism is a daily requirement for working with the nation's future children who have various characteristics. Professional teachers have teaching

experience, intellectual capacity, morals, faith, piety, discipline, responsibility, broad educational insight and managerial abilities.

The introduction of professional standards to raise and monitor requirements to certify teachers enhances the improvement of teacher quality and brings clarity and predictability into the system. This trend demands better trained and equipped teachers at the various levels of the educational sectors. Essentially, teacher professionalism is seen as the ability of the practitioners of the profession to enforce its rules and regulations in term of the knowledge base autonomy, responsibility, ethics, work conditions, training certification and registration. However, in Nigeria, the teaching profession is yet to be fully accorded the status of a profession because it has no direct and systematic control or adequate status because of lack of political will on the part of Teachers' Registration Council to enforce its code of ethics and standards. The nature of teacher professionalism in Nigeria is contested against a background of rapidly changing educational policies which do not position the teacher as the locus of change in the school system. Education in Nigeria today has undergone series of changes and every state by its transformation is spurred by the need to promote enlightenment and bring a just equalitarian and advanced society. To achieve this properly, teaching has to take its rightful place of being professional. Professionalism is a factor that aids quality education in a broad concept with having healthy and well-nourished learners that are ready to learn. Professionalism and quality education is needed and relates to learning environments that are healthy, safe, protective gender-sensitive, and provide adequate resources and facilities.

Education industry requires quality measures that are relevant to curricular content accompanied by apt materials for acquiring skills for life and knowledge in areas that promote the development of the country. Teacher is therefore ascribed with the description of quality education in the manner as conceptualizes education in a complex structure entrenched in a political, cultural and economic context. Education for All Global Monitoring Report (2014), contended that all over the world, there is a growing agreement about the need to provide access to education of good quality which is done by the teacher. The term "quality education" varies from country to country depending on cultural and economic importance attached.

Teaching programmed preparation across the country emphasizes three major elements via:

- Elements at preparing aspiring educators to possess and demonstrate the knowledge, skills and dispositions needed to be an effective instructor.
- Content knowledge that certainly necessary to provide learners with accurate information to be learned and later applied in life situations.
- Skills needed which is the pedagogy of teaching, the methods of instruction that peak a student's interest and make the learning meaningful and memorable.

Professionalism is multifaceted and therefore difficult to define (NPE, 2019). It is argued further that professionalism is divided into three categories which are professional parameters, professional behaviours, and professional responsibilities. It is clear from the foregoing that the roles of teacher in sustainable development cannot be quantified, especially, training personnel in various areas of the workforce. For national development and peaceful coexistence to be attained, there is need to give priority to investment in human capital through teacher education and training. The Nigerian education system needs to be responsive to the technological, social and economic needs of the society and provide the type of human resources needed in the industrial and economic sector. The issues of teacher preparation, supply, status enhancement, motivation and retention as well as

continuous training and retraining should be at heart of education reform at all levels (NAP, 2022). Afolabi (2017) stated that when Nigeria was under Colonial Masters, teachers were mainly priests and their assistants (pupil teacher), since the main aim of education then was the acquisition of literacy and numeracy skills for Evangelism and Book keeping. But today there is a National Teacher Education Policy in Nigeria, published in 2009 and it has seven key principles (Tijani & Daramola, 2015):-

KEY PRINCIPLES OF TEACHER EDUCATION

Principle 1: To attract competent people into the teaching profession, this must be with adequate incentives.

Principle 2: To produce capable teachers, admission and graduation requirements need to be reviewed to improve the quality of entrance and graduates.

Principle 3: For student teachers to be able to learn well, teacher education institutions must be equipped to prepare them adequately.

Principle 4: For teachers to be able to teach well at their level, they must have sufficient mastery of content and subject-specific methods of teaching.

Principle 5: Successful student teaching is a result of structured effective and supportive provided to the student teacher by a variety of educators.

Principle 6: Teacher educators must be sufficiently trained and capable of imparting and modeling desired knowledge, skill and attitudes.

Principle 7: Like all professionals, teachers must constantly upgrade their knowledge and skills if they are to remain relevant in a rapidly changing world (NTI, 2022).

There are teachers that are already teaching but not professionally qualified especially in most private primary and secondary schools. This is a gap in adherence to government policies between public and private schools especially on in-service training and continuous professional development. While government institutions strictly adhere to any directive, there is always less response from the private institutions. There is issue of quality and relevance that the teacher education curriculum especially NCE curriculum is very academic and less practical. The teacher education institutions have no facilities to encourage innovations, so many remediation goes on because of quality of the candidates going into teacher education. Most of the relevant agencies that supposed to implement the National Teacher Policies are either not having it or yet to implement it especially at the state and local government levels.

THE IMPORTANCE OF PROFESSIONALISM TO TEACHER

It is the belief that education is a moving element and never-ending process. This means that learning does not stop after earning a degree and starting a career. It goes through continuing education where career-minded individuals can constantly improve their skills and become more relevant and proficient at their jobs. It is very important for school administrators to encourage teachers to pursue professional development and productive career programmes. It does not only to ensure the best learning outcomes for the students but also to make them more effective and satisfied in aspects of their respective field of work.

These can be seen through:

Students have better learning outcomes

The work of the teacher is not complete if the students do not have better learning outcomes. School guidelines and curriculum standards are constantly changing, making it challenging for teachers to keep up with trends and best practices in the field. Professional development transforms teachers into better and more apt educators by enabling them to create relevant and tailored course instructions for today's students. Research by the U.S. Department of Education, Institute of Sciences Education concluded that student achievement can improve by as much as 21 percent as a result of teachers' participation in a well-designed professional development programs. National Board Certification is one path for teachers to pursue professional development and keep up with the latest educational standards to ensure optimal students learning.

Teachers learn better ways to teach

Teachers discover new teaching strategies through professional development, they are able to go back to the classroom and make changes to their lecture styles and curricula to better suit the needs of their students. However, these changes are hard to evaluate because they are implemented gradually. Professional skills make teacher to be more efficient in their presentations and course evaluations by exposing learners to new delivery methods, evaluation styles and record-keeping strategies.

Teachers develop better organization and planning skills

In addition to the hours spent presenting in the classroom, much of teachers' time is spent on student evaluations, curriculum development and other paperwork. Professional development training can help teachers to become better at planning their time and staying organized. This ultimately makes teachers more efficient and gives them extra time to focus on students rather than the paperwork.

Teachers gain knowledge and industry insight

Students expect teachers to be subject matter experts for the topics they teach. This means teachers should be able to answer any question a student throws their way. Professional development programs can enable teachers to expand their knowledge base in different subject areas. The more professional development a teacher undergoes, the more knowledge and industry insight he or she gains.

Teachers want to continue their education

It is easy for teachers to become burdened by the kind of teaching they are engaged. Professional development gives them an opportunity to step out of their routine - they get to be the student instead of the teacher. This keeps educator engaged because they feel like they are receiving the professional help they need to be better teachers. After all, professional development nurtures the talents of teacher who aspire to take on educational leadership positions and this, teachers must learn from other experienced teachers to become effective future leaders.

Implementing professional education development has benefits for both teachers and students, but most importantly, it helps teacher to become better educators and develop into competent future school administrators. The resources for administrators and teachers to develop skills and learn best practices according to the latest standards in the education field must be readily available. One development option for teachers who are interested in taking

on leadership roles and pursuing school administrator certification is the educational personal support and leadership skills where teachers need to stay current in the field (Schleicher, 2012).

Conclusion

Based on the discussion and findings about teachers` roles in enhancing professionalism in the education industry at improving the quality of education, the paper concludes that professional teachers who have pedagogic competence, personal competence, social competence, and professional competence strongly support the implementation of quality education in accordance with national education standards set by the government. The influence of professional teachers on student behavior is very significant during the teaching and learning process. Professional teachers are able to equip graduates with the competencies expected by parents, society and the world of work by motivating them to study well, complying with existing regulations. It can be concluded that as professional teachers, it is compulsory to have exemplary behaviour and attitude inside and outside of the classroom.

Recommendations

- The profession should embrace characters that encourage exhibiting total commitment and responsibility to be self-improved as real contribution for students learning.
- The system should establish an appropriate system of standards that can help all teachers work towards both high standards and the same professional status.
- Teachers should be supported with efforts to make them achieve professional status and effective professional learning activities through accountability, well defined policies of welfare and provision of facilities that are based on their needs.
- Teacher competences, knowledge, and skills in various learning activities of professional development must be strengthened and supported.
- There should be seriousness and commitment from stakeholders like community members and philanthropists so that education industry can achieve its goals.
- There should be consistency in supporting teachers and encourage innovation in teaching practice for the improvement of personal and other members of the school communities.

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